

Decentralized Indian Rupee: Stable Cryptocurrency for Indian Economy

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Abstract — Cryptocurrencies are being widely adopted by government and non-government organizations. A barrier that still exists to the widespread adoption is the high volatility of the cryptocurrencies. Stablecoins provide a solution for the high volatility of cryptocurrencies by providing price stability. There are two types of stablecoins, collateralized stablecoins and non-collateralized stablecoins. Collateralized stablecoins make use of other physical and digital assets to back up the cryptocurrency. Non-collateralized stablecoins make use of algorithms to deal with the price fluctuations. This paper introduces a non-collateralized stablecoin which will be pegged to the price of an Indian Rupee.

Keywords — cryptocurrency, stablecoin, digital asset, indian rupee, algorithmic, blockchain

I INTRODUCTION

Scarcity and use value are two crucial properties of money. Precious metals like gold and silver come under commodity money – those which are scarce and have non-monetary use value. One of the factors leading to the use of precious metals were that they were hard to counterfeit. The cost of producing commodity money is high and therefore, making multiple denominations was almost impossible. Fiat money lacks both absolute scarcity and non-monetary use value. High cost of counterfeiting and low cost to mint made the usage of fiat money possible. At the initial stages, the governments used to store commodity money, in their treasury, equivalent to the fiat money produced. From 1971 onwards, value of many of the fiat currencies primarily depend on the government's ability to use it as a payment.

Synthetic commodity has absolute scarcity and lacks non-monetary use value. This commodity was made possible due to the present-day institutional and technological infrastructure. The value of electronic form of money is guaranteed by a variety of financial institutions. Electronic money outside of fiat was not possible for a long time due to easy reproducibility of electronic information. With the advent of bitcoin, blockchain technology made it possible for electronic money outside of fiat to exist. Since cryptocurrencies like bitcoin are susceptible to high volatility, it cannot be used for day to day transactions.

There are vast varieties of regulated exchanges where different cryptocurrencies can be traded. They are also providers of market liquidity. These exchanges can be used as oracles of price discovery. This paper introduces DINR (Decentralized Indian Rupee), a new synthetic commodity which makes use of the blockchain technology. DINR has the security and decentralization offered by blockchain while having the price stability of fiat currencies.

II LITERATURE REVIEW

Evan Kuo and Brandon Iles [1] launched AMPL (Ampleforth) in 2019. AMPL is a purely algorithmic stablecoin which is pegged to US Dollar. It is completely decentralized. Ampleforth protocol has a governance token called FORTH, with which users can vote for any changes in the protocol. It is released as an ERC-20 (Ethereum Request for Comments - 20) token. It makes use of blockchain oracles to get price data from various third-parties. AMPL supply is changed by the smart contracts according to the price information from blockchain oracles in order to stabilize AMPL to US Dollar. Supply change only occurs if the AMPL price has exceeded or fallen beneath the defined threshold. Rebasing AMPL, if needed, is done every 24 hours.

Maker Foundation - Team of open-source engineers headed by Christensen [2] initiated the building of DAI currency. DAI is a decentralized algorithmic stable cryptocurrency. DAI is minted when someone uses other cryptocurrencies as a collateral to take loan. When the loan is paid back, DAI is burned and the collateral can be taken back. DAI is a collateralized cryptocurrency and is also algorithmically pegged to the US Dollar.

FRAX is an open-source [3] hybrid stablecoin. Hybrid stablecoin maintain low volatility by making use of both collaterals and algorithm. FRAX is a fractional-algorithmic stablecoin which is partially collateralized and partially stabilized algorithmically. FRAX protocol uses it's own governance token called FXS (Frax Shares). FXS can also be used to mint FRAX.

Tether Limited Inc. [4] launched a collateralized stablecoin called USDT in 2014. USDT is a centralized cryptocurrency which is pegged to the US Dollar. When one USDT is minted, an equivalent value of collateral is stored in the reserves. Since USDT is centralized, there is no way to guarantee that all the issued tether is 100% backed by reserves.

Binance [5] issued a US Dollar-backed stablecoin called BUSD. BUSD is 1:1 backed by US Dollar. It is a centralized cryptocurrency but the reserves are monthly audited by New York State Department of Financial Services. It is issued as an ERC-20 token and also supports BEP-2 (Binance smart chain Evolution Proposal - 2).

III MOTIVATION

Traditional fiat currencies are highly centralized. The issuing authority can decide whether to increase or decrease the supply. Transaction between entities at different countries is costly and can take considerable time. For successful completion of each transaction, a third-party must be trusted.

The downsides of fiat currencies can be solved by using cryptocurrencies. Since cryptocurrencies are built by using blockchain technology, most of them are decentralized and uncensored. Decentralized cryptocurrencies are not dependent on a single authority. Each transaction can be verified publicly, thereby providing high level of transparency and reliability. A transaction, once entered on the blockchain, cannot be modified. Cryptocurrencies have their own downsides. Cryptocurrencies are prone to high volatility. Due to the volatile nature, cryptocurrencies cannot be efficiently used for regular payments. In order to have sustainable payment using cryptocurrencies, the value of the cryptocurrency should remain relatively same during the entire lifetime of a contract.

The volatility issues of cryptocurrencies can be solved by using stablecoins. A stablecoin is a type of cryptocurrency whose value remains relatively stable. There are mainly two types of stablecoins:

- Collateralized Stablecoins
- Non-Collateralized Stablecoins

Collateralized stablecoins are backed up by valuable physical or digital assets. USDT, USDC and DAI are examples of collateralized stablecoins. These cryptocurrencies will be pegged to the value of the asset that is backed up. Such cryptocurrencies are in a way centralized, since the storage and release of assets are managed by a central authority. It brings back the disadvantages of fiat currencies.

Non-Collateralized stablecoins are not backed up by any kind of assets. Price of these cryptocurrencies are stabilized by using algorithms, therefore known as algorithmic stablecoins. They are usually pegged to the price of another valuable stable asset. AMPL, RAI and FEI are examples of non-collateralized cryptocurrencies.

DINR is a non-collateralized algorithmic stablecoin pegged to the Indian Rupee. DINR has the security and decentralization of blockchain and the price stability of fiat currencies. This will enable DINR to be used for even small transactions. Transactions are not limited by geographic boundaries and the cost of making a transaction is very small as compared to the traditional ones. There is no need to trust a third-party for making transactions. Since the blockchain network is maintained by a decentralized network of peers, no single authority can affect or censor DINR. All the transactions made using DINR are publicly verifiable. DINR can bridge traditional finance and decentralized finance in India.

IV METHODOLOGY

Smart contracts are the backbone of DINR. The algorithms needed to stabilize the price are stored in smart contracts. These smart contracts are deployed in the Ethereum blockchain network. When the price of 1 DINR is more than 1 INR, the supply of DINR is increased in order to bring its price back to 1 INR. When the price of 1 DINR is less than 1 INR, some of the issued DINR are burned in order to increase demand so that its price increases to 1 INR. The price of INR is obtained by using decentralized blockchain oracles.

IV.A Blockchain Oracle

Blockchain oracles are data feeds which bridge the outside world and the blockchain network. Off-chain data (data from outside the blockchain network) can be pulled from blockchain oracles. On-chain data (data from the blockchain network) can be pushed to blockchain oracles. They can source, verify and transmit external information. Based on trust models, blockchain oracles are of two types:

- Centralized Oracles
- Decentralized Oracles

In a centralized oracle, a central authority sources, verifies and transmits all the external information. It is prone to a single point of failure. A third-party has to be trusted in order to provide valid information.

In a decentralized oracle, there are several different data providers that source, verify and transmit external information. This removes the single-point of failure. It eliminates the need for blindly trusting a single third-party since the data can be validated from many other data providers.

DINR uses a market oracle system consisting of multiple decentralized blockchain oracles. The obtained data is guaranteed to be valid by the data providers from all the oracles used. The price of DINR across various exchanges can be obtained.

IV.B Re-base Contract

After getting the price of DINR, the value is passed to the rebase contract. Rebase contract decides whether to contract or expand the supply.

The supply of DINR is expanded or contracted according to two rules, provided a target price P_t and price threshold ζ :

1. If the rate of DINR is greater than $P_t + \zeta$, then the supply of DINR is expanded to the coin holders
2. If the rate of DINR is less than $P_t - \zeta$, then the supply of DINR is contracted from the coin holders

If the DINR price remains within the threshold band, the supply is not affected. Then, the price and supply of DINR is said to be in equilibrium.

DINR price at equilibrium has the following pattern:

Figure 1: Price-Equilibrium Series

DINR supply at equilibrium has the following pattern:

Figure 2: Supply-Equilibrium Series

Figure 4: Supply-Expansion Series

IV.C Stabilization Contract

Rebase contract sends the decision it has made to the stabilization contract. Stabilization contract finds out the number of tokens that must be burned if the supply is to be contracted or minted if the supply is to be expanded. The DINR supply is minted to or burned from all the user wallets. For example:

- If the price of 1 INR equals 1.5 DINR, the price can be brought to equilibrium by increasing each wallet's balance by 50%.
- If the price of 1 INR equals 0.5 DINR, the price can be brought to equilibrium by decreasing each wallet's balance by 50%.

C.1 Expansion

When the price of DINR exceeds the upper threshold, the supply is expanded in each user wallet according to the offset percentage. The increase in supply results in the decrease in demand and therefore, brings the price back to equilibrium.

Figure 3: Price-Expansion Series

After supply expansion, the price can go back to where it began from but the supply would end up higher from where it began.

C.2 Contraction

When the price of DINR falls beneath the lower threshold, the supply is contracted in each user wallet according to the offset percentage. The decrease in supply results in the increase in demand and therefore, brings the price back to equilibrium.

Figure 5: Price-Contraction Series

Figure 6: Supply-Contraction Series

After supply contraction, the price can go back to where it began from but the supply would end up lower from where it began.

V EXPLANATION

The system tries to keep the price of DINR at equilibrium. When the price exceeds or falls behind the threshold price, the DINR supply is expanded or contracted, respectively. Changing the supply alone will not affect the DINR price directly. The decentralized network of actors affect the price by adjusting their bids. Actors are the ones who are actively involved in the buying and selling of DINR. Actors respond to changes in supply based on how quickly or slowly they think others will respond.

The decentralized network of actors can be categorized into two:

- Slow Actors
- Fast Actors

Slow actors are ones who hold assets for a long period of time without getting involved in frequent trading. Fluctuations in price and supply does not affect slow actors.

Fast actors are ones who perform frequent trading and monitors the market for any fluctuations to take advantage of. There are three states for DINR market:

1. Before supply change, s0
2. During supply change, s1
3. After supply change, s2

Scenario I (Expansion):

Let FA be a fast actor who has 1 DINR in his wallet. FA monitors the DINR market during it's three states:

At s0:

FA has 1 DINR worth 1.2 INR per DINR

At s1:

FA has 1.2 DINR worth 1.2 INR per DINR

At s2:

FA has 1.2 DINR worth 1 INR per DINR

At s1, FA has an opportunity to sell more DINR for the same price than he could have at s0. Fast actors who take advantage of this market state brings down the price of DINR to equilibrium.

Scenario II (Contraction):

Let FA be a fast actor who has 1 DINR in his wallet. FA monitors the DINR market during it's three states:

At s0:

FA has 1 DINR worth 0.8 INR per DINR

At s1:

FA has 0.8 DINR worth 0.8 INR per DINR

At s2:

FA has 0.8 DINR worth 1 INR per DINR

At s1, other fast actors can buy greater percentage of DINR from FA at the same price than they could have at s0. Fast actors who take advantage of this market state brings up the price of DINR to equilibrium.

VI IMPLEMENTATION

Get Data From Oracle

```
function getData() external payable returns (uint256, bool) {
    uint256 reportsCount = providers.length;
    uint256[] memory validReports = new uint256[](reportsCount);
    uint256 size = 0;
    uint256 minValidTimestamp = block.timestamp - reportExpirationTimeSec;
    uint256 maxValidTimestamp = block.timestamp - reportDelaySec;

    for (uint256 i = 0; i < reportsCount; i++) {
        address providerAddress = providers[i];
        Report[] memory reports = providerReports[providerAddress];

        uint8 index_recent = reports[0].timestamp >= reports[1].timestamp ? 0 : 1;
        uint8 index_past = 1 - index_recent;
        uint256 reportTimestampRecent = reports[index_recent].timestamp;
        if (reportTimestampRecent > maxValidTimestamp) {
            // Recent report is too recent.
            uint256 reportTimestampPast = providerReports[providerAddress][index_past]
                .timestamp;
            if (reportTimestampPast < minValidTimestamp) {
                // Past report is too old.
                emit ReportTimestampOutOfRange(providerAddress);
            } else if (reportTimestampPast > maxValidTimestamp) {
                // Past report is too recent.
                emit ReportTimestampOutOfRange(providerAddress);
            } else {
                // Using past report.
                validReports[size++] = providerReports[providerAddress][index_past].payload;
            }
        } else {
            // Recent report is not too recent.
            if (reportTimestampRecent < minValidTimestamp) {
                // Recent report is too old.
                emit ReportTimestampOutOfRange(providerAddress);
            } else {
                // Using recent report.
                validReports[size++] = providerReports[providerAddress][index_recent].payload;
            }
        }
    }

    if (size < minimumProviders) {
        return (0, false);
    }

    return (Select.computeMedian(validReports, size), true);
}
```

```
function rebase() external onlyOrchestrator {
    require(inRebaseWindow());

    // This comparison also ensures there is no reentrancy.
    require(lastRebaseTimestampSec.add(minRebaseTimeIntervalSec) < block.timestamp);

    // Snap the rebase time to the start of this window.
    lastRebaseTimestampSec = block
        .timestamp
        .sub(block.timestamp.mod(minRebaseTimeIntervalSec))
        .add(rebaseWindowOffsetSec);

    epoch = epoch.add(1);

    uint256 cpi;
    bool cpiValid;
    (cpi, cpiValid) = cpiOracle.getData();
    require(cpiValid);

    uint256 targetRate = cpi.mul(10**DECIMALS).div(baseCpi);

    uint256 exchangeRate;
    bool rateValid;
    (exchangeRate, rateValid) = marketOracle.getData();
    require(rateValid);

    if (exchangeRate > MAX_RATE) {
        exchangeRate = MAX_RATE;
    }

    int256 supplyDelta = computeSupplyDelta(exchangeRate, targetRate);

    if (supplyDelta > 0 && uFragments.totalSupply().add(uint256(supplyDelta)) > MAX_SUPPLY) {
        supplyDelta = (MAX_SUPPLY.sub(uFragments.totalSupply())).toInt256Safe();
    }

    uint256 supplyAfterRebase = uFragments.rebase(epoch, supplyDelta);
    assert(supplyAfterRebase <= MAX_SUPPLY);
    emit LogRebase(epoch, exchangeRate, cpi, supplyDelta, block.timestamp);
}
```

```
function rebase(uint256 epoch, int256 supplyDelta)
    external
    onlyMonetaryPolicy
    returns (uint256)
{
    if (supplyDelta == 0) {
        emit LogRebase(epoch, _totalSupply);
        return _totalSupply;
    }

    if (supplyDelta < 0) {
        _totalSupply = _totalSupply.sub(uint256(supplyDelta.abs()));
    } else {
        _totalSupply = _totalSupply.add(uint256(supplyDelta));
    }

    if (_totalSupply > MAX_SUPPLY) {
        _totalSupply = MAX_SUPPLY;
    }

    _gonsPerFragment = TOTAL_GONS.div(_totalSupply);

    emit LogRebase(epoch, _totalSupply);
    return _totalSupply;
}
```

VII RESULT

Cryptocurrencies can be made stable without using any type of collateral assets. Security, decentralization and price stability can be incorporated together in cryptocurrencies. DINR bridges the gap between traditional finance and decentralized finance. It can be used for day to day transactions without incurring additional costs or being censored.

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